

QUARTERLY EVALUATION OF NUTRIENTS AND HEAVY METALS VARIABLES IN AGODO-EGBE WETLAND AREA IKOTUN LAGOS

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands play a crucial role in maintaining ecological balance, biodiversity preservation, and providing essential ecosystem services to both the environment and human populations. However, they face constant threats from climate change, rapid urbanization, unmanaged settlements, and invasive species. The Agodo-Egbe wetland area in Ikotun, Lagos, Nigeria, is a critical ecological site with low-lying topography and varying water sources. This study aimed to trimestral assess the nutrients and heavy metals variables in the wetland, focusing on heavy metals and nutrient concentrations inconsistency across the quarters. The data collected showed significant differences in nutrient and heavy metal levels across quarters and sampling stations, indicating potential environmental changes. The findings of a two-factor ANOVA highlighted significant differences in nutrient variables across quarters but not across heavy metal types. Based on the wide-ranging analysis, recommendations for effective management and conservation include continuous monitoring, source identification, risk assessment, remediation strategies, stakeholder engagement, adaptive management, and long-term conservation planning. Continuous monitoring will provide vital data for informed decision-making and proactive management of the wetland ecosystem. Source identification, risk assessments, remediation strategies, and stakeholder engagement are crucial for reducing nutrient enrichment and heavy metal pollution in wetland ecosystems.

Key Words: Biodiversity Preservation, Agodo-Egbe Wetland, Ikotun, Nutrient, Metals.

INTRODUCTION

Wetlands are fundamental for ecological balance, biodiversity preservation and providing essential ecosystem services to both the environment and human populations. However, they are

under constant threat from changing climate patterns, rapid urbanization, unmanaged settlements and invasive species. Notably, the Agodo-Egbe Wetland Area in Ikotun, Lagos, stood out due to its unique characteristics and ecological importance. Yet, this region faces significant anthropogenic pressures, including urban development, agriculture and industrial activities, which can profoundly impact the ecological health of the wetland, particularly concerning water quality and pollutant accumulation (Adeolu *et al.*, 2021).

Conserving the Agodo-Egbe wetland is imperative for preserving local biodiversity, regulating water quality and safeguarding its ecosystem services. Assessing nutrient and heavy metal variables in the area is essential for maintaining environmental health, addressing pollution, and promoting community well-being. Accurate data on these variables will guide conservation efforts and the development of sustainable wetland management strategies, shedding light on the potential impact of human activities on the wetland and local communities. This assessment of nutrients and heavy metals in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area is a critical step toward comprehending, preserving and managing this vital natural resource for current and future generations (Albeto *et al.*, 2021).

The Minnesota Pollution Control Agency (MPCA) underscores the importance of biological monitoring programs that collect water chemistry data from wetlands. These data serve various purposes, including evaluating water quality, biological condition criteria, watershed restoration, and standards development. Water testing in wetlands involves measuring parameters like pH, specific conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and water temperature to assess water quality and its suitability for supporting aquatic life. Aquatic ecosystems play a fundamental role in upholding water quality and providing stability for various uses.

Regular water testing in wetlands is crucial for ensuring environmental health and reaping the multitude of benefits they offer, including ecological, economic, and social advantages. Wetlands serve as habitats for diverse plant and animal species, provide critical migratory bird stopovers, and offer essential resources for both humans and wildlife. However, these ecosystems are increasingly threatened by pollution, habitat loss, and climate change (Omer, 2023). Therefore, regular water testing is instrumental in detecting and addressing pollution before it poses a significant risk to wetlands. It also serves as a vital tool for monitoring the effectiveness of wetland restoration initiatives, rehabilitating degraded wetland ecosystems, and ensuring their continued environmental health.

The confluence of rapid urbanization, industrialization, population growth and limited environmental awareness presents a global threat to precious freshwater resources, which are indispensable for providing crucial ecosystem services to humanity. Ensuring the quality and sustainability of freshwater bodies is of utmost importance as it constitutes less than 1% of Earth's total water. This is particularly true in light of the environmental challenges posed by heavy metals, which are inherently carcinogenic and can cause severe harm to DNA, proteins, and lipids through the generation of free radicals (Adetunji *et al.*, 2020). These heavy metals, including essential and non-essential categories, enter the environment through both natural processes and human activities, such as industrial discharges, automobile emissions and mining (Mandla *et al.*, 2021).

The Agodo-Egbe wetland area in Lagos State, particularly in Ikotun Lagos, requires a comprehensive assessment of nutrient and heavy metal variables. Nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, are crucial for supporting aquatic vegetation and maintaining wetland health. However, excessive nutrient loading can lead to negative outcomes like eutrophication, harmful algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and biodiversity loss. Heavy metals, such as lead, cadmium, and mercury, pose significant threats to aquatic and terrestrial life and ecosystem integrity (Adejomoke, 2018). The assessment of these variables is vital for environmental health, biodiversity conservation, human well-being, policy formulation, and long-term sustainability of the region. The findings can inform environmental policies, promote sustainable land use practices, and address environmental challenges such as nutrient imbalances, heavy metal pollution, biodiversity loss, lack of baseline data, and inadequate regulatory framework. Despite these challenges, the wetland's ecological significance remains significant. This study aims to quarterly assess the nutrients and heavy metals variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland, determining heavy metals variables, assessing nutrients variables, and comparing variations in water samples collected from different locations and periods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Agodo-Egbe wetland area in Ikotun, Lagos, Nigeria with the GPS co-ordinate of (6°52'94.17"N, 3°28'77.13"E), is a critical ecological site in Lagos State. It is characterized by its low-lying topography, making it susceptible to changes in water levels. It is surrounded by urban and peri-urban areas, including residential neighborhoods, roads and small-scale

industries. The wetland is a freshwater wetland ecosystem with varying water sources, including rainfall, runoff and small tributaries. It supports diverse flora and fauna, including aquatic plants, fish species and bird populations. The surrounding land is subject to multiple land uses, including residential, agricultural, industrial and recreational activities. Human settlements and agriculture may contribute to potential nutrient runoff and pollution. Threats to the wetland include urbanization and industrialization as well as pollution from nearby sources like heavy metals, agricultural runoff and solid waste. Conservation is essential for maintaining local biodiversity, regulating water quality, providing recreational and aesthetic value to the community.

Water samples were collected from two different points within the wetland once every quarter in 2023 to assess water quality, focusing on the level of heavy metals and nutrient concentrations. Randomly sampling techniques was adopted for select sampling points within the wetland area to minimize bias and capture potential hotspots of nutrient and heavy metal concentrations. Water sampling bottles were used to collect water samples within the wetland. Field Notebooks was used for recording field observations, data and taking notes during field work. Statistical software such as SPSS was used for the descriptive statistics and to analyze the data for ANOVA.

Fig. 1: The Agodo-Egbe wetland showing the sampling locations (Source: Google Earth Pro)

Determination of Nutrients: A portion of the sample was filtered through a $0.45\mu\text{m}$ glass fiber filter. The filtrate was used for the determination of ammonia ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$), nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$), nitrite ($\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$), dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP), total dissolved nitrogen (TDN), and dissolved organic nitrogen (DON).

Nitrate-nitrogen (NO_3) (mg/L): Nitrate-nitrogen was determined on an aliquot of the filtered sample following a cadmium reduction method (SM 4500 B, HACH Method 8192) with NitraVer-5 reagent powder. Test solutions were measured at 500 nm using a HACH DR 3900 spectrophotometer. Nitrite-nitrogen was determined on an aliquot of filtered sample by diazotization using Nitrite reagent powder (HACH Method 10019). Test solutions were determined at 525 nm using a HACH DR 3900 spectrophotometer. Ammonia-nitrogen was determined on an aliquot of the filtered sample by the salicylate method using a salicylate/cyanurate reagent. Test solutions were measured at 655 nm (HACH Method 8155).

Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN) (mg/L): The concentration of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) is the sum of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ given by the equation:

$$\text{Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN)} = \text{NO}_3\text{-N} + \text{NO}_2\text{-N} + \text{NH}_3\text{-N}$$

where:

$\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ is ammonia. $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ is nitrate, and $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ is nitrite.

Dissolved Organic Nitrogen (DON) (mg/L): An aliquot of the filtered sample was used for the determination of Total Dissolved Nitrogen (HACH Method 10072), following an alkaline persulfate digestion at 105 °C for 30 min, which converts all forms of nitrogen to nitrate. Nitrate then reacts with chromotropic acid under strongly acidic conditions to form a yellow complex, in proportion to the TDN concentration. The test solution was measured at 410 nm. Don was then determined by the difference. The concentrations of dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) were estimated by subtracting DIN from TDN.

$$\text{Dissolved organic nitrogen (DON)} = \text{TDN} - \text{DIN}$$

where;

TDN is total dissolved nitrogen after persulfate oxidation. DIN is the sum of the dissolved inorganic nitrogen species.

Phosphate-Phosphorus (reactive phosphorus) (PO_4^-) (MG/L): Sample Pre-treatment Mild Digestion for the Determination of SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and SiO_2 : An aliquot (50 ml) of the well-mixed sample was transferred into a conical flask. To this was added 5 mL of 6M HCl, which was then heated on a hot plate until the volume had been reduced to about 30 ml. The digestant was cooled and then filtered through Whatman filter paper. The residue on the filter was washed with distilled water. The filtrate was quantitatively transferred to a 50-ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with distilled water, and saved for the determination of sulfate, silica, and phosphate.

Phosphate was determined using the Ascorbic Acid Method (HACH Method 8048, SM 4500-P E). Phosphorus was determined by the molybdenum blue method, in which ascorbic acid was used to reduce the complex to an intense blue color. The measurement was made at 880 nm using a spectrophotometer and recorded in mg/L.

Dissolved inorganic phosphate (mg/L): this was determined using the ascorbic acid reduction method. A portion of the sample was filtered through a 0.45 μm glass fiber filter. The filtrate was used for the determination of DIP (as PO_4). An aliquot of the filtrate was reacted with molybdate

in an acid medium (PhosVer 3 reagent powder, Hach Method 8048) to produce a mixed phosphate/molybdate complex. Ascorbic acid in the reagent then reduces the complex to an intense blue color, which is proportional to the phosphate concentration. The measurement was made at 880 nm using a HACH DR 3900 spectrophotometer.

Sulphate (mg/L): Sulfate was determined using the turbid-metric method (SM 4500 E HACH 8051). An aliquot of sample filtrate from a digested sample was reacted with barium chloride (HACH SulfaVer 4 reagent powder). The amount of turbidity in the test solution is proportional to the sulfate concentration and was determined at 450 nm using a spectrophotometer, with the readings expressed in mg/L.

Silica (SiO₂) (mg/L): The silica was measured using a colorimeter. To 10 ml of the sample was added 0.2 ml of hydrochloric acid (HCL), followed by 0.4 ml of moly-date reagent. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes, and 0.4 ml of an already prepared reducing solution was added. Silica concentration was determined at 600 nm using a pre-calibrated colorimeter (DR2010), and the readings were expressed in mg/L.

Determination of Heavy Metals: The heavy metals were determined in the filtrate of the sample digestate by optical emission spectrometry using inductively coupled plasma (Agilent ICP-OES 710 Axial EPA Method 200.7). Test results were validated with calibration curves obtained with certified metal standards (Accu Standard Incorporation, United States of America). The pre-treatment of water samples through hot plate digestion for metal determination involved placing 100 ml of each water sample into a clean 100 ml beaker, adding 5 ml of HNO₃, and heating the mixture on a hot plate at 100 °C for 30 min. The solution was diluted to 100 ml with deionized water and then filtered through Whatman #1 filter paper. The filtrate was saved for the determination of the metals.

Copper (mg/L): Copper levels were obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 324.754 nm.

Iron (mg/L): Iron quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 259.940 nm.

Zinc (mg/L): Zinc levels were obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 213.857 nm.

Cadmium (mg/L): Cadmium levels were obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 226.502 nm.

Chromium (mg/L): Chromium quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 226.502 nm.

Manganese (mg/L): Manganese quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 257.610 nm.

Arsenic (mg/L): Arsenic quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 188.979 nm.

Lead (mg/L): Lead quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 220.353 nm.

Nickel (mg/L): Nickel quantitation was obtained with Agilent Expert II software on a wavelength of 231.604 nm.

Procedure for Data Analysis

Data Preparation: All collected data was organized in a tabular form including measurements of water quality parameters, nutrient concentrations, heavy metal levels, ecological observations, and any other relevant data.

Data Visualization: Visual representations of the data were created using graphs and charts. This helps in identifying patterns and trends.

Hypothesis Testing: The hypothesis was tested to determine if there are statistically significant differences or relationships among variables using either ANOVA or Multivariate regression. The regression analysis enabled us to model relationships between variables.

PRESENTATION OF RESULT

The results of a study to quarterly evaluate the variables relating to nutrients and heavy metals on the Agodo-Egbe wetland area in Ikotun, Lagos State, are presented herein. Water samples were collected in two sampling stations (St. 1 and St. 2) in each of the quarters of the year 2023 and tested for nutrient and heavy metals. The result obtained is as presented in table 1 and 2 below.

Table 1: Quarterly Water Chemistry Data of the Nutrients Variables at the Wetland in Agodo-Egbe area of Ikotun Lagos, 2023

S/N	VARIABLES	January, 2023		April, 2023		July, 2023		October, 2023		Mean	STDEV	CV	EM (Z = 1.96)
		St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2				
1	Nitrate (mg/L, as NO ₃ ⁻)	7.180	10.220	3.850	3.910	2.245	0.627	0.991	2.609	3.954	3.257	82.375	3.192
2	Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (mg/L)	1.621	2.307	0.869	0.883	0.507	0.142	0.223	0.589	0.893	0.735	82.374	0.721
3	Dissolved Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)	0.033	0.012	0.042	0.035	0.040	0.043	0.047	0.050	0.038	0.012	31.393	0.012
4	Particulate Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)	0.109	0.006	0.077	0.065	0.049	0.043	0.037	0.031	0.052	0.031	60.474	0.031
5	Sulphate (mg/L)	2.900	2.300	3.000	2.300	2.350	2.240	2.130	2.020	2.405	0.354	14.702	0.347
6	Phosphate (mg/L, as PO ₄ ³⁻)	3.940	3.810	3.410	2.520	2.255	1.789	1.323	0.857	2.488	1.151	46.247	1.128
7	Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus (mg/L)	1.313	1.270	1.137	0.840	0.752	0.597	0.442	0.286	0.830	0.383	46.195	0.376
8	Silica (mg/L, SiO ₂)	21.110	21.900	27.700	23.120	26.415	27.598	28.781	29.964	25.824	3.334	12.913	3.268

(St.: Sample Station, STDEV: Standard Deviation, CV: Coefficient of Variance, EM: Error Margin)

Table 2: Quarterly Water Chemistry Data of the Heavy Metals Variables at the Wetland in Agodo-Egbe area of Ikotun Lagos, 2023

S/N	VARIABLES	January, 2023		April, 2023		July, 2023		October, 2023		Mean	STDEV	CV	EM (Z = 1.96)
		St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2	St. 1	St. 2				
1	Zinc (mg/L)	0.099	0.010	0.100	0.200	0.201	0.240	0.279	0.318	0.181	0.104	57.322	0.102
2	Iron (mg/L)	0.403	0.401	0.390	0.389	0.383	0.377	0.372	0.367	0.385	0.013	3.397	0.013
3	Arsenic (mg/L)	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	41.309	0.000
4	Copper (mg/L)	0.300	0.251	0.160	0.141	0.071	0.015	0.049	0.099	0.136	0.099	72.900	0.097
5	Cadmium (mg/L)	0.062	0.050	0.028	0.049	0.032	0.026	0.020	0.014	0.035	0.017	48.253	0.017
6	Lead (mg/L)	0.022	0.020	0.019	0.011	0.009	0.006	0.002	0.002	0.011	0.008	72.969	0.008
7	Chromium (mg/L)	0.030	0.029	0.042	0.030	0.036	0.037	0.039	0.040	0.035	0.005	14.215	0.005
8	Manganese (mg/L)	0.480	0.480	0.281	0.520	0.421	0.413	0.405	0.397	0.425	0.073	17.166	0.071
9	Nickel (mg/L)	0.074	0.031	0.092	0.062	0.071	0.074	0.076	0.079	0.070	0.018	25.422	0.017

(St.: Sample Station, STDEV: Standard Deviation, CV: Coefficient of Variance, EM: Error Margin)

Determination of the Variation in Nutrient and Heavy Metals

The spatial variation in heavy metals and nutrient concentration in the water samples collected from two sampling stations (St1 and St2) each in January, April, June and October, 2023 was tested for using ANOVA. The result is as presented in table 3 and 4 as well as figure 2 and 3 below.

Table 3: Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication for Quarterly Water Data of the Nutrients Variables at the Wetland in Agodo-Egbe area of Ikotun Lagos, 2023

<i>SUMMARY</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Row 1	8	31.632	3.954	10.60866
Row 2	8	7.1408	0.8926	0.540625
Row 3	8	0.3016	0.0377	0.00014
Row 4	8	0.4164	0.05205	0.000991
Row 5	8	19.24	2.405	0.125029
Row 6	8	19.904	2.488	1.32391
Row 7	8	6.6368	0.8296	0.146865
Row 8	8	206.588	25.8235	11.11862
Column 1	8	38.206	4.77575	49.00291
Column 2	8	41.825	5.228125	56.01907
Column 3	8	40.085	5.010625	86.2779
Column 4	8	33.673	4.209125	60.17425
Column 5	8	34.6125	4.326563	80.63902
Column 6	8	33.0786	4.134825	90.55237
Column 7	8	33.9735	4.246688	98.79841
Column 8	8	36.406	4.55075	106.3172

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Rows	4236.635	7	605.2336	187.8978	3.91E-33	2.203232
Columns	9.221053	7	1.317293	0.40896	0.892174	2.203232
Error	157.8328	49	3.221078			
Total	4403.689	63				

Table 4: Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication for Quarterly Water Data of the Heavy Metals Variables at the Wetland in Agodo-Egbe area of Ikotun Lagos, 2023

<i>SUMMARY</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Row 1	8	1.4468	0.18085	0.010747
Row 2	8	3.0812	0.38515	0.000171
Row 3	8	0.00392	0.00049	4.1E-08
Row 4	8	1.08698	0.135873	0.009811
Row 5	8	0.28008	0.03501	0.000285
Row 6	8	0.0902	0.011275	6.77E-05
Row 7	8	0.28296	0.03537	2.53E-05
Row 8	8	3.39684	0.424605	0.005313
Row 9	8	0.55976	0.06997	0.000316
Column 1	9	1.4718	0.163533	0.032883
Column 2	9	1.2732	0.141467	0.034877
Column 3	9	1.1128	0.123644	0.017578
Column 4	9	1.4033	0.155922	0.033802
Column 5	9	1.2238	0.135978	0.026202
Column 6	9	1.18721	0.131912	0.02766
Column 7	9	1.2418	0.137978	0.027359
Column 8	9	1.31483	0.146092	0.027375

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Rows	1.645229	8	0.205654	65.18947	1.41E-25	2.108688
Columns	0.010491	7	0.001499	0.475063	0.848579	2.178156
Error	0.176664	56	0.003155			
Total	1.832383	71				

Fig. 2: Quarterly variation of the mean nutrient variables

Fig. 3: Quarterly variation of the mean Heavy Metals variables

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1 presents the quarterly water chemistry data of nutrients variables at the Agodo-Egbe wetland in Ikotun, Lagos, for 2023. This data is crucial for understanding the quality of the water and assessing potential impacts on the ecosystem and human health. The variables measured include nitrate, dissolved inorganic nitrogen, dissolved organic nitrogen, particulate organic nitrogen, sulfate, phosphate, dissolved inorganic phosphorus, and silica. Nitrate levels vary across quarters and sampling stations, with higher values observed in January and April compared to July and October. Dissolved inorganic nitrogen levels show variability but are generally lower than nitrate levels, indicating different sources or processes influencing nitrogen availability in the water. In their research on seasonal variations of nitrogen and DOC, Andrea and Francesc (2005) came to this conclusion. Dissolved organic nitrogen levels remain relatively low and stable, suggesting consistent inputs or cycling of organic nitrogen compounds in the wetland water. Particulate organic nitrogen levels are also relatively low, but some variability is observed between quarters and sampling stations, possibly reflecting changes in organic matter input or sediment dynamics within the wetland. Sulfate levels show minor fluctuations across quarters and sampling stations, suggesting consistent sources or processes contributing to sulfate in the wetland water. Phosphate levels exhibit variability similar to that of nitrate, with higher concentrations observed in January and April compared to July and October. Dissolved inorganic phosphorus levels show variability but generally lower concentrations compared to phosphate, emphasizing the importance of considering different forms of phosphorus in assessing nutrient dynamics in the wetland. Understanding these trends and variances is essential for conservation and management decisions in order to maintain the wetland and its biodiversity, according to the study by José et al. (2014).

The Agodo-Egbe wetland in Ikotun, Lagos, has quarterly water chemistry data for heavy metal variables for 2023. These data are shown in Table 2. This information is essential for determining the toxicity and possible contamination levels of heavy metals in the wetland ecosystem, which can have serious effects on the environment and public health. Zinc levels vary across quarters and sampling stations, with some fluctuations observed between January, April, July, and October. The variability may be influenced by factors such as industrial activities, runoff from urban areas, or natural geological processes, as stated by Francis and Taylor in their study on the influences of natural anthropogenic factors on surface and groundwater quality in rural and urban areas (Sanjiv, 2015). Iron concentrations show minor fluctuations across quarters and sampling stations, with concentrations remaining relatively stable over time. However, the levels are generally higher compared to other heavy metals, possibly indicating natural

sources or weathering of iron-rich minerals in the wetland. Arsenic levels are consistently low and close to or below detection limits across all quarters and sampling stations, as arsenic is a highly toxic heavy metal that poses serious health risks to humans and ecosystems. Copper concentrations exhibit variability across quarters and sampling stations, with some fluctuations observed between January, April, July, and October. Cadmium levels show fluctuations across quarters and sampling stations, with concentrations generally remaining within a relatively narrow range. Lead concentrations vary across quarters and sampling stations, as even low levels of exposure can pose risks to human health and aquatic organisms. Chromium levels exhibit minor fluctuations across quarters and sampling stations, with concentrations remaining relatively stable over time. Comprehending these patterns and fluctuations is crucial for well-informed management and remediation actions that safeguard the wetland ecosystem and lessen possible health risks to human populations, as stated by (Jenny et al., 2013) in their study.

The findings of a two-factor ANOVA without replication for quarterly water data on nutritional variables in the Ikotun Lagos wetland area of Agodo-Egbe in 2023 was displayed in Table 3. Each row and column in the table has summary statistics that show the count, sum, average, and variance of the data. The rows and columns of the ANOVA table indicate the causes of variance in the data. The degrees of freedom represent the number of independent pieces of information available to estimate a parameter. The mean square represents the average variation within each factor. The F-statistic is a ratio of two variances, indicating the significance of the difference between group means. The p-value indicates the probability of obtaining the observed results if the null hypothesis is true. The critical F-value is used to determine whether the observed F-value is statistically significant. The ANOVA results show that there are significant differences in nutrient variables across different quarters of the year (rows), but no significant differences across different types of nutrients (columns). The error term represents the unexplained variation in the data, which is not attributable to the rows or columns. The total row provides the total variation in the data.

In 2023, the Agodo-Egbe wetland area of Ikotun Lagos conducted a two-factor ANOVA without replication to analyze quarterly water data on heavy metal variables. The results are shown in Table 4. The analysis includes summary statistics for each row and column, including the count, sum, average, and variance of the data. The ANOVA Table shows that the variation among rows (different quarters) is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting significant differences in heavy metals variables across different quarters of the year. However, the variation among columns (different heavy metals) is not statistically significant (0.848579), implying no significant differences in heavy metal variables across

different types of heavy metals. The error represents the unexplained variation in the data, and the total provides the total variation in the data. In summary, the ANOVA results indicate significant differences in heavy metals variables across different quarters of the year (rows) but no significant differences across different types of heavy metals (columns). This analysis helps in understanding the variation in heavy metal content in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area of Ikotun Lagos throughout the year.

Fig. 2 shows the quarterly change of mean nutrient variables in the Ikotun Lagos wetland area of Agodo-Egbe. Between January and October, the mean nitrate content exhibits a declining tendency, which could be attributed to biological processes, human activity, or weather patterns, as agreed with the study on the on the different seasonality of nitrate from agricultural waste water by (M. et al., 2016). Dissolved inorganic nitrogen and dissolved organic nitrogen also show a decreasing trend, possibly due to seasonal fluctuations in organic matter decomposition and microbial activity. Particulate organic nitrogen levels show some variability, with a decrease observed from April to October, possibly due to sedimentation rates and biological processes. Sulfate concentrations show slight fluctuations, with a decrease observed from July to October, possibly due to rainfall patterns, mineral weathering, and anthropogenic activities. Phosphate levels show a decreasing trend from January to October, indicating potential changes in phosphorus dynamics within the wetland ecosystem. Dissolved inorganic phosphorus concentrations also show a decreasing trend, suggesting potential changes in phosphorus availability and cycling. Silica concentrations show an increasing trend from January to October, indicating potential changes in silica sources or inputs. Overall, the quarterly variation of nutrient variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area underscores the importance of regular monitoring and assessment to understand ecosystem health and inform management strategies.

The quarterly variation of heavy metal variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area of Ikotun Lagos is presented in Fig. 3. Zinc concentrations show an increasing trend from January to October, possibly due to potential inputs from industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, or atmospheric deposition. Iron levels are relatively stable, with minor fluctuations observed. Arsenic concentrations remain low and consistent, often associated with natural geological sources and anthropogenic activities. Copper concentrations show a decreasing trend from January to October, suggesting potential mitigation efforts or changes in copper inputs. Cadmium levels show a decreasing trend, suggesting potential changes in cadmium sources or environmental conditions affecting its mobility and bioavailability. Lead concentrations show a decreasing trend, possibly reflecting improvements in environmental management practices or reductions in lead emissions from anthropogenic sources. Chromium concentrations show slight fluctuations, with no

clear increasing or decreasing trend observed. Manganese levels show minor fluctuations, with concentrations remaining relatively stable. Generally, the quarterly variation of heavy metal variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area underscores the importance of monitoring and understanding the dynamics of heavy metal pollution in wetland ecosystems to support effective management and conservation efforts.

CONCLUSION

An in-depth examination of the quarterly assessment of heavy metal and nutrient variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area of Ikotun Lagos offers priceless insights into the dynamics of the water chemistry and possible environmental effects within the ecosystem. The study reveals significant variations in nutrient and heavy metal concentrations across different quarters and sampling stations, highlighting the complex interplay of natural processes and anthropogenic activities influencing water quality. For nutrient variables, the findings indicate notable fluctuations in nitrate, dissolved inorganic nitrogen, phosphate, and silica levels throughout the year, suggesting dynamic nutrient cycling processes within the wetland ecosystem. These variations are crucial for understanding the ecosystem's health and informing management strategies to preserve biodiversity and mitigate potential environmental risks. To reduce the negative effects of heavy metal pollution on ecosystem integrity and public health, monitoring and remediation efforts are crucial. Analyzing heavy metal variables also reveals distinct seasonal trends in the concentrations of zinc, copper, cadmium, lead, and chromium. To sum up, the Agodo-Egbe wetland area in Ikotun Lagos's quarterly assessment of nutrient and heavy metal variables is an essential tool for sustainable management practices and well-informed decision-making that protect the region's ecological balance and human welfare. The long-term health and resilience of the wetland ecosystem in the face of persistent environmental problems are ensured by this study, which emphasizes the significance of continual monitoring and conservation activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the comprehensive analysis conducted on the quarterly evaluation of nutrient and heavy metal variables in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area of Ikotun Lagos, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Continuous Monitoring:** Sustain regular monitoring efforts of water chemistry parameters, including both nutrient and heavy metal variables, to track long-term trends and detect any significant changes in water quality. This will provide crucial data for informed decision-making and proactive management of the wetland ecosystem.

2. **Source Identification:** Conduct further investigations to identify specific sources of nutrient and heavy metal inputs into the wetland, including industrial activities, agricultural runoff, urbanization, and natural geological processes. Understanding the sources of contamination will facilitate targeted management strategies to mitigate potential impacts on water quality.
3. **Risk Assessment:** Conduct comprehensive risk assessments to evaluate the potential ecological and human health risks associated with elevated levels of nutrients and heavy metals in the wetland ecosystem. Assessments should consider exposure pathways, toxicity thresholds, and sensitive receptor populations to guide prioritization of management actions.
4. **Remediation Strategies:** Develop and implement remediation strategies to reduce nutrient enrichment and heavy metal pollution in the wetland environment. This may include habitat restoration, sediment management, and pollution prevention measures aimed at minimizing pollutant inputs and enhancing ecosystem resilience.
5. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Foster collaboration and engagement with local communities, government agencies, academic institutions, and other stakeholders to raise awareness about water quality issues in the Agodo-Egbe wetland area. Encourage active participation in monitoring efforts and decision-making processes to promote shared responsibility for wetland conservation and management.
6. **Adaptive Management:** Adopt an adaptive management approach to address evolving challenges and uncertainties associated with water quality management in the wetland ecosystem. Regularly review monitoring data, assess management effectiveness, and adjust strategies as needed to achieve desired conservation outcomes.
7. **Long-term Conservation Planning:** Develop comprehensive, science-based conservation plans to guide sustainable management and protection of the Agodo-Egbe wetland area over the long term. Incorporate principles of ecosystem-based management, resilience, and adaptive governance to ensure the continued health and integrity of the wetland ecosystem for future generations.

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